

MANUFACTURING PATTERNED CARBON FIBER CATHODES BY SUPERCRITICAL SPRAY: SIMULTANEOUS ENHANCEMENT OF ELECTROCHEMICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF STRUCTURAL BATTERY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The shift toward zero-emission mobility for urban, air, and space transport requires transformative advances in structural energy storage. Carbon fiber reinforced polymer structural battery composites (CFRP-SBCs) present a compelling opportunity by integrating load bearing and energy storage capabilities. However, their practical deployment in electric aviation and e-VTOL applications is hindered by two fundamental challenges: low energy density and compromised mechanical performance. Herein, we introduce a sustainable, scalable manufacturing approach utilizing supercritical spray deposition to engineer tailorable 3D nanostructures on carbon fiber cathodes. By manipulating the amphiphilicity and droplet size of hybrid suspensions containing lithium iron phosphate (LFP) and reduced graphene oxide (rGO), distinct post-evaporation patterns, rings, domes, and disks/domes, are formed. These patterns modulate interfacial properties and electrochemical behavior, enabling the concurrent enhancement of energy density and interfacial strength, previously considered challenging. Our results show that disk/dome patterned cathodes perform better in electrochemical properties (energy density, power density, capacity) while ring patterned cathodes show higher interfacial adhesion. These results demonstrate that combining multiple patterns enables synergistic improvements in both mechanical and functional performance. This platform paves the way for the development of high-strength, high-energy-density composite systems critical to enabling future e-mobility applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for zero-emission vehicles for urban, air and space mobility has reignited interest in battery-powered electric mobility (e-mobility). Particularly, reshaping aviation toward a greener future by 2050 [1] will not be realized without addressing challenges in battery technology in electric flights and electric vertical take-off and landing (e-VTOL) aircrafts. Carbon fiber reinforced polymer battery composites (CFRP-SBCs), comprising polymers as electrolyte matrix and carbon fibers (CFs) as electrodes, collectors and reinforcements show a perfect synergy between structural performance and energy efficiency. However, a significant hurdle is the considerably lower energy

density (less than 40 Wh/kg in full cell configuration) [2-4] compared to the conventional batteries as well as the minimum required 400-600 Wh/kg for small-medium size planes [5], and their significantly reduced strength and stiffness (2-10 GPa modulus and \sim 100-200 MPa strength, 20-30% of structural CFRPs). This is arising from the inherent tradeoff between mechanical and electrochemical properties and the historical separation of batteries and structures. This is a common trait in almost all engineered materials, in which efforts to enhance multiple functions, such as energy storage and structural properties, face complexity as improvements in one compromise others. Particularly in CFRP-SBCs, two bottlenecks to achieve simultaneous high energy density and high mechanical strength are: (1) Very low ion transport in solid polymer electrolytes (10^{-6} - 10^{-5} S.cm⁻¹) compared to liquid (10^{-2} S.cm⁻¹) and ceramics (10^{-5} - 10^{-3} S.cm⁻¹). (2) Requirement of abundant coating of active materials on carbon fiber cathodes to reach reasonable energy density that results in weakening the interfacial adhesion with the electrolyte (and separator) that causes delamination and premature mechanical failure. Herein, we introduce scalable and green manufacturing techniques without the use of harsh solvents, wherein engineered patterns are fabricated on cathode to create tailorable microstructure for simultaneously high strength and high energy density in CFRP-SBCs.

To address the limitations of conventional lithium-ion batteries and build upon insights from prior studies demonstrating the substantial influence of nanopatterning on the mechanical robustness, thermal stability, and electrical conductivity of composites, this work explores the impact of engineered nanopatterns on LFP-rGO cathode structures. Although various fabrication techniques such as sol-gel, [6], electrophoretic deposition (EPD) [7], high-temperature reduction strategy [8], drawdown method [9], and high-energy ball milling assisted by the rheological phase method [10] have been employed to create LFP/rGO composites, these approaches do not sufficiently enable the engineering of nanoscale surface morphologies. This study, therefore, investigates optimal strategies for manipulating surface patterns to achieve desired nanoscale architectures and examines how different nanopatterns affect cathode performance. The motivation for this inquiry is rooted in evidence that tailored nanopatterns not only improve interfacial adhesion between substrates such as carbon fiber and the polymer matrix, but also significantly enhance the multifunctional performance of composites without compromising mechanical integrity [11]. By extending this concept to battery cathodes, we hypothesize that specific nanopatterning strategies can markedly improve the electrochemical performance and durability of LFP-rGO systems, offering a new pathway for advanced cathode design. This exploration specifically focuses on the influence of disk/dome and ring structures patterned on cathode surfaces within structural battery composites (SBCs), aiming to bridge the current knowledge gap in this domain. Through systematic analysis of both fabrication processes and the resulting electrochemical behavior, the study demonstrates the potential of nanoscale engineering to significantly enhance battery performance [12, 13]. These efforts are supported by the adoption of innovative fabrication techniques, notably a precision spray-deposition method, which enables controlled pattern formation and offers refined balance between power output and specific capacity, thereby embodying a rigorous approach to electrochemical tuning and optimization for LFP-rGO cathodes [11, 14-26].

Our novel, scalable and sustainable processing-manufacturing technology, in which a combination of supercritical spray technique and tailorable materials chemistry (via engineering amphiphilicity) allows creation of 3D patterns on carbon fiber-based cathodes. These patterns are combined to create desired 3D nanostructures to achieve tailorable properties. To this end, the droplet size and amphiphilicity degree of the hybrid material system contained in droplets, i.e. lithium iron phosphate (LFP) and reduced graphene oxide (RGO), are engineered based on their mass ratio and then delivered onto the carbon fibers using supercritical spray. The droplet sizes are in the range of 5 μ m, as the small microscale droplets allow for faster fabrication of cathode with higher surface area that incurs higher interface with the developed electrolyte. The combination of amphiphilicity and droplet size results in three distinctive post-evaporation patterns, i.e. ring, disk, and dome. Each pattern is meticulously designed to enhance a specific functionality or property. By strategically composing these patterns with precise shape, size, and spacing, we achieve the creation of 3D nanostructured surfaces that exhibit both high energy density and exceptional mechanical strength, qualities often deemed paradoxical and unattainable with conventional manufacturing methods. The outcomes of our study are emerging key materials and a novel high-throughput manufacturing technique required for accelerated development of the next-generation multifunctional structures for battery-powered and eco-friendly mobility.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reduced graphene oxide (rGO) used in this study was sourced from ACS Material and synthesized via the N_2H_2 chemical reduction method. It appeared brownish-grey, had a thickness of approximately 1 nm, and exhibited a monolayer diameter ranging from 0.5 to 10 μm with over 90% monolayer content. Its BET surface area was measured at $\sim 180 m^2/g$, and carbon content exceeded 82 wt.%, with electrical conductivity surpassing 500 S/m. Lithium iron phosphate (LFP) from Landt International Inc. featured a particle size median (D50) of 1.302 μm , a surface area of 13.36 m^2/g , and a density of 1.14 g/cm^3 . Its discharge capacity was recorded at 153 mAh/g under 0.1C at 25 °C, highlighting its electrochemical effectiveness. To fabricate composite cathodes, rGO was strategically incorporated into LFP using spray-deposition at two mass ratios: 8:1 (LFP:rGO) to produce ring-like patterns and 1:1 for dome structures. The materials were dispersed at 1.5 wt.% in dimethylformamide (DMF) and subjected to a two-step sonication process. First, LFP was sonicated at 53% amplitude for 10 minutes. Then, rGO was added and the mixture underwent an additional 20-minute sonication. The dispersion was sprayed onto acetone-cleaned aluminum substrates (19 mm diameter), which were chosen to match the dimensions required for coin cell cathodes. Each spray round was performed at 20 MPa pressure, maintaining a 15 cm distance and a 45° nozzle angle to ensure uniform coating. Pauses between rounds allowed solvent evaporation, preventing droplet agglomeration. The active material deposited was approximately 4 mg for the 8:1 sample (2.68 mg/cm^2) and 4.4 mg for the 1:1 sample (2.95 mg/cm^2). Coin cells were assembled in an argon-filled glove box using the coated cathodes, $LiPF_6$ electrolyte, lithium metal anodes, separators, spacers, and crimped stainless steel casings. Surface morphology of the deposited patterns was evaluated using a Bruker DektakXT Surface Profiler, while microstructural analysis was conducted via a Tescan FERA-3 FIB microscope. Electrochemical characterization involved cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic charge/discharge measurements (2.0–4.25 V) using a Gamry Interface 1010E potentiostat, with CV conducted at 0.1 mV/s for 10 cycles. Specific capacities were reported based on the total mass of the LFP/rGO electrodes. We also evaluated the adhesion strength of the active material to the substrate by measuring weight loss in the tape adhesion test. The test was conducted with a 200 g for the first eight cycles, followed by 1540 g and 6540 g for the second and third eight-cycle stages, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cathodes Morphology

The LFP/rGO dispersion was applied to aluminum substrates/current collectors using a precision spray-deposition method. Compositions with varying LFP to rGO weight ratios were prepared and labeled as LFP/rGO-(Y:Z), where 'Y:Z' denotes the respective mass ratios. A total of 25 spray passes were performed using a 1.5 wt.% solution to deposit each formulation.

Figure 1 presents scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the deposited LFP/rGO ring and disk/dome patterns. These images reveal that LFP nanoparticles are predominantly encapsulated by rGO sheets and interconnected with neighboring particles following the evaporation of DMF. Figure 1a illustrates a ring-shaped pattern formed by the droplet, while Figures 1B and 1C show the material distribution at the center and periphery of the same pattern. In contrast, Figures 1E and 1F show a disk/dome pattern, where the composite material is concentrated along the outer diameter of the droplet. Compared to the dome pattern, where material is centered, the ring pattern is characterized by an empty core with materials pushed to the perimeter. These distinct morphologies arise from variations in the LFP/rGO ratio used in the spray solution.

Figure 2 provides further morphological and elemental analysis using SEM and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Figure 2a displays a SEM image of a dried droplet from an LFP/rGO-(8:1) mixture, revealing the expected ring pattern, characterized by concentrated Fe and P signals around the droplet perimeter, with a distinct void in the center. Figures 2B and 2C, showing iron (Fe) and phosphorus (P) EDS maps, confirm this ring shape distribution. In contrast, Figures 2D, 2E, and 2F examine a droplet from an LFP/rGO-(1:1) formulation. Here, the SEM and EDS maps illustrate a disk/dome morphology, marked by high material density in the center and gradual thinning toward the edges.

The use of a spray-deposition approach on aluminum current collectors enables the formation of well-defined microscale patterns, ranging from rings to disks and/or domes, on the substrate surface. These patterns are dictated by the composition and amphiphilic balance of the hybrid nanoparticle suspension. Our study shows that higher rGO content, such as in the LFP/rGO-(1:1) mixture, favors disk-shaped deposits, where the droplet dries to form a dense, raised center composed of overlapping rGO-LFP clusters. In contrast, lower rGO content (e.g., LFP/rGO-(8:1)) results in ring-like patterns due to differential solvent evaporation dynamics, pushing the particles outward.

Figure 1. SEM image of LFP/rGO left after evaporation of sprayed droplets on the Al substrate/current collector cathode: A) Ring pattern (LFP/rGO-(1:1)), B) Center of the ring pattern, C) Outer diameter of ring pattern, D) Disk/Dome pattern (LFP/rGO-(8:1)), E) Outer diameter of the disk/dome pattern, F) Center of disk/dome pattern.

Figure 2: SEM, EDS maps and profilometry of LFP/rGO left after evaporation of sprayed droplets on Al substrate/current collector cathode A) SEM image of ring pattern (LFP/rGO-(1:1)), B, C) EDS

of ring pattern (Fe, P), D) SEM image of disk/dome pattern (LFP/rGO-(8:1)), E, F) EDS element mapping of the dome pattern (Fe, P)

3.2 Electrochemical and Mechanical Properties

The interface between the cathode and electrolyte plays a critical role in determining the electrochemical performance of lithium-ion batteries. As such, the ability to control the deposition pattern of active materials during fabrication offers a promising strategy to tailor cathode functionality. In this study, we investigated how distinct deposition patterns, namely disk and ring structures, influence the performance of LFP/rGO cathodes. Electrochemical characterization was performed using cyclic voltammetry (CV) at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s, comparing patterned cathodes against a classic LFP formulation (LFP:PVP:Carbon Black at 93:2:5 wt.%) (Figure 4a). Both ring and disk-patterned cathodes displayed symmetrical redox peaks, indicative of good reversibility, though notable differences emerged. The disk-patterned electrodes showed sharper peaks and higher current responses than their ring counterparts, suggesting enhanced reaction kinetics and improved charge transfer efficiency. This was further supported by a smaller voltage separation between oxidation and reduction peaks, pointing to reduced polarization. While the ring pattern exhibited broader peaks and slightly lower peak currents (~80–85% of disk), its more gradual charge transfer dynamics may be advantageous under high-rate cycling, reducing parasitic losses and extending durability.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) provided further insights into charge transfer behavior (Figure 4b). The charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of the classic LFP cathode was significantly higher (~380 Ω) compared to both patterned variants, 220 Ω for ring and 150 Ω for disk/dome, highlighting the improved conductivity introduced by rGO. When normalized to the weight of active materials, the disk/dome-patterned cathode delivered the highest specific power and energy output, approximately 486 W/kg and 44.12 kWh/kg, while the ring-patterned version followed closely with about 10% lower values. The classic LFP cathode, by contrast, exhibited significantly lower performance in all metrics (Figure 4C).

Mechanical integrity was assessed using adhesion testing (Figure 4D), which monitored residual weight loss over multiple tape-peeling iterations. Among the three designs, the ring-patterned cathode demonstrated the slowest rate of material removal, as evidenced by the smallest slope magnitude (-2.41×10^{-4} g/iteration), indicating superior adhesion. In contrast, the classic LFP cathode exhibited the fastest material loss (-8.05×10^{-4} g/iteration), suggesting weaker cohesion. This enhanced adhesion in the ring pattern is attributed to its more compact microstructure and reduced rGO content, which minimizes lubrication effects between LFP particles. Additionally, the ring geometry, with a taller and thinner outer wall, offers a larger interfacial area and improved mechanical interlocking with the electrolyte layer, further contributing to its robust adhesion performance.

Mechanical integrity was assessed using adhesion testing (Figure 4D). Interestingly, the ring-patterned cathode exhibited approximately 25% higher tangential friction force compared to the disk/dome, indicating stronger cohesion and greater resistance to delamination. This is attributed to the lower rGO content in the ring structure, as rGO tends to act as a lubricant between LFP particles. The enhanced compactness of the ring configuration results in a more mechanically robust microstructure. Tape-adhesion tests and triboindenter results corroborated these findings. Notably, the ring pattern, characterized by a thin outer wall with an average height three times greater than that of the disk/dome structure, offers a larger interfacial area and improved mechanical interlocking with the electrolyte layer.

In summary, while disk/dome-patterned cathodes deliver superior electrochemical performance in terms of peak current, specific capacity, and output power, the ring-patterned design excels in structural robustness and interfacial stability. These complementary traits suggest that combining ring and disk/dome patterns through a controlled spray-deposition process could yield a hybrid cathode architecture optimized for both performance and durability. This hybrid approach offers greater design flexibility than traditional slurry casting, enabling tailored electrode architectures for next-generation structural battery composites.

Figure 4. Electrochemical performance comparison of LFP:rGO cathodes with disk/dome and ring patterns: A) Cyclic voltammetry, B) Nyquist plot, C) Maximum power density and Energy density, and D) Adhesion mechanical test.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that nanoscale surface patterning of active materials on cathodes, achieved through precision spray deposition, offers a powerful strategy to tailor the electrochemical and mechanical performance of lithium-ion batteries. By systematically varying the weight ratio of LFP to rGO in the spray dispersion, we produced distinct surface morphologies, disk/dome and ring patterns, that led to measurable differences in battery behavior. Electrochemical tests revealed that disk/dome-patterned cathodes deliver superior energy densities, indicating enhanced conductivity and faster charge transfer. In contrast, ring-patterned cathodes exhibit improved mechanical integrity and greater cohesion at the electrode–electrolyte interface, owing to their toroidal geometry and more compact structure.

These results highlight the trade-offs and synergies inherent in cathode design: while disk/dome patterns optimize electrochemical output, ring patterns contribute to structural durability and interfacial stability. The ability to precisely control and combine these patterns on the electrode surface introduces a novel degree of freedom in cathode engineering, offering the potential to pre-design multifunctional electrodes that achieve an optimal balance between performance and longevity. This pattern-directed strategy significantly advances the conventional two-dimensional slurry-based fabrication methods and opens new avenues for customizable, high-performance structural battery composites.

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